

A Convenient Preparation of 2,6-Dimethoxyphenylacetic Acid

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Yoshiro Ogata, *et al*¹ investigated the condensation of monochloroacetic acid with naphthalene and some of its derivatives and obtained naphthyl-1-acetic acid and substituted naphthylacetic acids respectively. We tried this reaction with various derivatives of benzene but none of them reacted except resorcinoldimethyl ether which gave a good yield of 2, 6-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid^{2,3} identified by mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample.

Procedure.—A mixture of resorcinoldimethyl ether (57.6 g.), monochloroacetic acid (14.2 g), ferric oxide (0.88 g) and potassium bromide (0.2 g) were placed in a long-necked flask fitted with a thermometer dipping into the reaction mixture and an air condenser about one meter long. The mixture was boiled gently on a sand bath. The temperature rose to 200° after 10 hr. and to 214° after 20 hr. It was then cooled and steam distilled to recover the unreacted resorcinoldimethyl ether. The residue in the flask was collected, extracted with hot sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave 2,6-dimethoxyphenyl acetic acid; yield, 8 g., m.p. 147°.

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